

THE SHUHUR SAN : DATE EQUIVALENCIES, ORIGINS AND SPECIAL PROBLEMS

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I. INTRODUCTION

Scholars working with Deccani materials from the fourteenth century onwards are familiar with the dating era called the Shuhūr San variously called Sur San, Shahur Sān, Arabi San, etc. Tables and/or discussions of the era are found in both Marāṭhi works and English works. But there are discrepancies in the treatment of the era—for example, Tables do not agree, there is confusion concerning what is actually the first day of each year, and quick calculations (such as subtracting 599 from the Christian year) are not necessarily accurate. By combining English Marāṭhi sources (M. Nāzīm, G. H. Khare, and B. F. Modak), tables are available from the last quarter of the fifteenth century through the nineteenth century; and L. D. Swamikannu Pillai offers tables covering the entire period although not immediately relating to the Shuhūr San. The Tables are inconsistent, unfortunately, and there is no single source which gives as lucid explanation of the intricacies involved in calculating date equivalencies; therefore, there is no way to judge which tables can be used with the greatest degree of accuracy and confidence.

This essay will attempt to resolve the problems of the Shuhūr era; first, there will be a brief introduction to the era; then, an explanation of the reasons for the discrepancies in existing source for setting the initial day of each Shuhūr year; thirdly, a method for calculating Shuhūr date equivalencies will be presented; and, finally, there will be a detailed analysis of various specific problems of calendar equivalencies relevant to understanding the calendar systems involved.

This essay has been written because of the interest and help of a number of scholars, professional persons, and institutions. Dr. Z. A. Desāi, Superintending Epigraphist for Arabic and Persian Inscriptions of the Archaeological Survey of India, Nagpur, and Dr. A. A. Kādiri, Senior Epigraphical Assistant in the same office, drew my attention to some of the problems involved in the Shuhūr San and suggested bibliography. Dr. G. N. Morje, Head of the Marāṭhi Department, Ahmednagar College, very kindly helped locate Marāṭhi sources and translated the relevant passages for me. And Faculty members, professional persons and staff connected with Deccan College, Poonā, the Archaeological Survey of India, South-Western Circle, Aurangābād, and Ahmednagar College, Ahmednagar, have assisted me in various phases of the research. I hope that this article will not only contribute to the study of South Asian History, but also serve as a demonstration of my thanks for their help and confidence.

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE SHUHŪR SAN

One of the earliest descriptions in English of the Shuhūr San was given by James Grant Duff in 1826 :

The *Mirg* or cultivator's year, always commences in the beginning of our month of June, corresponding with the end of the Hindoo month, *Veyshak*, or beginning of *Jeshṭ*.....

By calculation, it appears that the Soorsun, (generally written Shuhoorsun by the Mussulmans), was introduced on the Mirg, in Heejree 745, which corresponds with A. D. 1344-45; and hence it would appear, that it must have originated with Mohummud Tughluq Shah. It was much more like his character, than that of the emperor Akber, to introduce so useless an innovation; but it was in the reign of Akber that the Fussiee era commenced to the north of the Nerbuddah, and it was introduced into the Deccan by his grandson, Shah Jahan, in the year of the Heejree 1047, or A.D. 1637-38. The Soorsun and Fussiee eras are merely solar years, setting out with the date of the Heejree when they commenced, but without making allowance in future reckoning, for the difference between the solar and lunar years; but which means they differ rather more than three years every century. Both the Soorsun and Fussiee are called Mirg, or the husbandman's year, from their commencing at the season when the fields begin to be sown.¹

Grant Duff's comments can be summarized in three categories. The first of these is the information about the era which is agreed upon by other authorities: the Shuhūr San is a solar era; the first day of any single Shuhūr year corresponds with the 'Mirg'—i.e., the day when the sun enters the Nakshatra Mrigasīras; and, since the Shuhūr year is calculated on a solar basis, it diverges from the Hijri year because each Shuhūr year contains more days than each Hijri year. Additional information from other authorities confirmed by records using Shuhūr dates, indicates that the Shuhūr year is 599 to 600 years behind the Christian year (from about June through December it is 599 years behind, and from January to about June it is 600 years behind; and, that although the Shuhūr and Hijri years begin on different dates, any particular day in Shuhūr era is identified by the Hijri nomenclature for that day.

The second category of Grant Duff's comments is his opinion that it was a "useless innovation". The continued use for several centuries of the Shuhūr San by different dynasties and different rulers suggests exactly the opposite. G. H. Khare points out that except for military documents it was used for most official records, particularly those which had to do with land and land revenue.² Upon reflection, its suitability for record-keeping seems obvious: by embracing a complete agricultural year, records concerning land and land revenue could be immediately understood without adjustment. And since the year began with the sowing season and, therefore, NEAR THE ONSET OF THE MONSOON, not only was organised material relevant for tax computation immediately available, but so was also information necessary for budgetary projections and estimations. In terms of an economy based heavily on agriculture, this was a more efficient time-period than a calendar year which changed at about the time of the spring harvest, as by early June some intimation of the potential of the monsoon was available for anticipating the yields of the coming year, and for planning broader budgetary considerations. Thus, for record-keeping purposes in the Deccan, it was an extremely logical calendar period.

The final category of comments has to do with calculations. Grant Duff says that the year begins in early June corresponding with the Hindu luni-solar months of Vaisakha or Jyestha; however, according to other authors, the year begins as early as 23 May and as late as 7 June. Furthermore, he suggests that calculations indicate that the year apparently was introduced in A.H. 745 (1344-45 A.D.). To verify these statements, a systematic method for finding date

¹ James Grant Duff, *A History of the Marhattas*, Vol. I (London, 1826), pp. 55-56.

² G. H. Khare, *Companion to Researchers* (Poona, 1951), p. 112.

equivalencies must first be established, and in order to do this, certain idiosyncrasies of the Christian calendar *vis-a-vis* the Hindu luni-solar calendar must be examined.

III. CHRISTIAN CALENDAR PROBLEMS

Long before the period of the Shuhūr San, the Julian calendar was in effect in the Christian countries of Europe. By the end of the sixteenth century, the Vernal Equinox which had originally fallen on the 21st of March came regularly on the 11th of March. In 1582 Pope Gregory declared that, in all Roman Catholic countries, ten days were to be omitted—the fifth of October was to be the fifteenth of October—in order to correct this shift and to bring the Vernal Equinox back to the 21st of March. In addition, all years evenly divisible by four were to have one extra day (i.e., the 29th of February) except in the case of the beginning of a century when only the first two digits had to be evenly divisible by four. That is to say, the years 1600 and 2000 were to be leap years, while the years 1700, 1800, and 1900 would not be, as the first two digits cannot be evenly divided by four.

The Gregorian reforms, however, were not instituted immediately in the Protestant and Orthodox sections of the Christian world. Of particular importance for South Asianists, they were not accepted in England. The result was that the English Old style calendar was out of step with the Gregorian calendar. From 5 October 1582 until 28 February 1700, the English calendar was ten days behind; and, because the English calendar continued to have a leap year in all years divisible by four, from that date until the English calendar reform in 1752, the English calendar was eleven days out of phase. The English reform took place when 2 September 1752 was followed by 14 September 1752, omitting the eleven day disparity between the calendars and establishing the Gregorian calendar in England.

For those scholars working with materials from the sixteenth century onwards, this raises the problems of reconciling Christian dates with one another. From October 1582 to the end of February 1700 sources which are Roman Catholic (e.g. French, Portuguese, etc.) have a ten day discrepancy; from then until 1752 the discrepancy is eleven days. Furthermore, reforms in Orthodox countries (e.g., Russia, Greece, etc.) did not occur at the same time as the English reform, and in some cases this discrepancy continued into the twentieth century, becoming greater in 1800 and 1900 where the old style Julian calendar prevailed.

In regard to Indian materials, the eleven days omitted by the 1752 reform had the effect of moving all days backward—e.g., any date which before the reform had fallen regularly on 8 May, since the reform omitted eleven days, then fell on 20 May. And any occasion falling with regularity near the end of May, then shifted into early June. So the major reason for the May/June discrepancy in references to the Shuhūr San is due to the English calendar reform.

This does not explain the discrepancy completely, as different authorities say that the variation in days between the two calendars was from 23 May to 25 May and from 5 June to 7 June (plus two days, plus eleven days, plus two days, or four days more than the calendar changes explain). This additional disparity is due to the different methods used to calculate the length of the Hindu solar year and the Christian solar year.

Technically, the Christian year is calculated on the basis of the time interval between one Vernal Equinox and the next, a period of a little less than 365 days and six hours. The Hindu

solar year is calculated on the basis of the time required for the earth to complete one revolution around the sun measured in relation to the (apparently) fixed stars, a period of a little more than 365 days and six hours. This time difference means that over a long period of time, the Christian calendar will gain slightly on the Hindu calendar; if a Hindu solar date is equal to 23 May for many years, it will then shift to 24 May, and after many more years it will shift to 25 May.¹

This is the same relationship which is seen between the Hijri lunar calendar and the Christian solar calendar, but in this instance the discrepancy is about eleven days per year and the gain is very rapid. As the disparity between the Christian calendar and the Hindu solar calendar is only a few minutes per year, it takes many years for even a one day discrepancy to appear. But, whenever tables embracing a long period of time are presented in which the opening day of the *Shuhūr* year always corresponds with the same Christian date (with—as in *Nāzīm*—or without—as in *Khare*—allowance for leap year additions), the tables are obviously fallacious and have not taken into account this shift.

IV. THE CALCULATION OF *SHUHŪR* SAN EQUIVALENCIES

One source which gives the scholar enough information with which to accurately calculate *Shuhūr* San equivalencies is Pillai's *An Indian Ephemeris*.² Pillai explains the era briefly, saying that its current year is 599 years behind the Christian year, and that each year begins when the sun enters the Nakshatra *Mrigasīras*. In a footnote, he gives an example of how to calculate the first day of any particular year, but without explanation: (1) the sun enters the Nakshatra *Mrigasīras* when his (the sun's) longitude is 53 degrees 20 minutes (2) the number of days which correspond to this longitudinal figure equals 56; and (3) when the solar year begins as in 1911 on 13 April, the sun's entry into the Nakshatra *Mrigasīras* would be 56 plus 13, or 69 days from 1 April, i.e., on 8 June.³

This example in Pillai's footnote, although it is not particularly clear, describes the procedure for calculating the first day of the *Shuhūr* year. What Pillai does not explain is that the entrance of the sun into the Nakshatra *Mrigasīras*, because it is a solar phenomenon, takes place every year the same number of days after the beginning of the solar year—i.e. 56 days after the solar new year. Since the first month of the solar year is *Mēsha* in Sanskrit and *Chittirai* in Tamil, the first day of the solar year will be found in Pillai's tables as 1 *Mēsha-Chittirai* in the column labelled "Solar Reckoning", under the heading "Cyclic Sidereal year, month, and day". In bold type, corresponding either to the month of March or April, 1 *Mēsha-Chittirai* will be seen, and reading across the line the equivalent Christian and Hijri dates will be given. For reasons which will be explained in the section on "The Indian Civil Day", the information must be read from the tables and not taken from the top of the page which gives the moment of *Mēsha Sankrānti*. Because the entrance of the sun into the Nakshatra *Mrigasīras* occurs 56 days later, 56 must be added to the March/April date of 1 *Mēsha-Chittirai* in the tables. To facilitate these calculations, Pillai has included information in all the volumes in the form of an end paper or a book marker entitled "Table III: Days of the English Calendar Year, reckoned cumulatively from March 1 and April 1 respectively", as well as in the Eye Tables, section g, found in Volume 1 Part 1 on pp. 156-57, 162-63, and 168-69 at the top of the pages.

¹ Actually a simple shift from 23 to 24 to 25 May is not immediately apparent because of the interpolation of a leap year day every four years. This phenomenon and the resultant pattern will be carefully examined in the section "Mēsha Sankrānti Equivalencies: An Unusual Pattern".

² L. D. Swāmikannu Pillai, *An Indian Ephemeris*, 7 volumes (Madras, 1922 and 1925).

³ *Ibid.*, Vol. I, part I, p. 55 and f.n.

In order to calculate the first day of the Shuhūr year equivalent to 1413, for example, the tables indicate that 1 Mēsha-Chittirai fell on the equivalent Christian date of 27 March (even though the actual moment of Sankrānti was 26.86 March in the Surya Siddhānta and 26.79 in the Ārya Siddhānta). To find the date corresponding to 56 days later, Table III is used, the column referring to cumulative days from the first of March. To the 27th day of March, 56 is added, giving a total of 83. The first of May is 62 days from the first of March; and 83 minus 62 will be 21 days after the first of May, or 22 May.

27 March equals 1 Mēsh-Chittirai
 +56 days more until sun enters
 the Nakshatra Mrigasīras.
 83 days from 1 March
 -62 days between 1 March and
 1 May.
 21 days after 1 May
 +1 May
 22 May

As another example of this procedure, to find the beginning of the Shuhūr year which occurred in 1783, the Pillai tables show that 1 Mēsha-Chittirai corresponded with 10 April. Since the date is being calculated from 1 April, 10 is added to the 56 days necessary for the sun to enter the Nakshatra Mrigasīras, totalling 66. The first of June was 62 days after 1 April, and 66 minus 62 gives a difference of 4 days after 1 June, or 5 June 1783. According to this procedure, since Table III gives the number of days corresponding to the first of the month, a date equivalency will always be X number of days after the first of the month, and so it is necessary to add 1: the day 6 days after 1 June is 7 June; the days 25 days after 1 May is 26 May, and so forth.

10 April equals 1 Mēsha-Chittirai
 +56 days more until sun enters
 the Nakshatra Mrigasīras.
 66 days from 1 April
 -62 days between 1 April and
 1 June.
 4 days after 1 June
 +1 June
 5 June

(For those who find no confusion in numbers, there is a slight modification of Pillai's method which simplifies the calculations. During the period of the use of the Shuhūr San, all the days 1 Mēsha-Chittirai fell either in March or April, and all the corresponding first days of each Shuhūr San year fell respectively in May and June. The time from 1 March to 1 May is 62 days, and the time from 1 April to 1 June is also 62 days. Since 1 needs to be subtracted with Pillai's method, the actual difference is 61. So to calculate an exact answer, one need only to subtract 61 from the total of the days of 1 Mēsha-Chittirai PLUS 56, remembering that a March date corresponds with a May date, and an April date corresponds with a June date.)

For most scholars, however, calculating the first day of any particular Shuhūr year corresponding with a Christian year is not of itself of interest. What is wanted is a method to find a Christian date equivalent to a particular Shuhūr date. If the only information given is a particular year—say Shuhūr 823—then the addition of 599/600 gives the equivalent Christian years, i.e. 1422/23. Checking Pillai's tables for those two years, Mēsha-Chittirai began on 26 March both years, and 26 plus 56 totals 82. Referring to Table III, 1 May was 62 days from 1 March, so that the first day of the Shuhūr San in both 1422 and 1423 fell on 82 minus 62 plus 1 May, or 21 May. The Shuhūr year 823 began on 21 May 1422 and ended the day before the next year began, that is on 20 May 1423.

In a case in which both a Shuhūr year and a Hijrī year are given but with no additional information, an even more precise calculation can be made. For example if the Shuhūr year 823 and the Hijrī year 826 are given, since Shuhūr year 823 embraced 21 May 1422 through 20 May 1423, then the time shared by these two years was from 15 December 1422 (when Hijrī 826 began) to 20 May 1423.

Finally, there is the case in which a complete *Shuhūr* date is cited, as 1 *Shawwāl Shuhūr* 965. Adding 599/600 to 965 gives 1564/65 as the equivalent Christian years. Pillai's Hijri tables indicate that there was only one 1 *Shawwāl* which fell into that period, occurring on 2 May 1565.

Since the solar *Shuhūr* year is longer than the lunar Hijri year, some part of the Hijri calendar will be repeated in each *Shuhūr* year—e.g., if 1 *Muharram* in a normal 354 day Hijri year should happen to fall on the first day of the *Shuhūr* year, then the Hijri year would expire after 354 days while the *Shuhūr* year continues to run, and a second 1 *Muharram* would fall in that *Shuhūr* year. The eleven days which are repeated would then be distinguished as *awwal* (first) and *ākhar* (last) days. Or if 10 *Ṣafar* should happen to correspond with the first day of a *Shuhūr* year, then 355 days later 10 *Ṣafar* would again be the Hijri date in the next Hijri year, but the 365 day *Shuhūr* year would still be running; in this case the dates 10 through 21 *Ṣafar* would be identified as *awwal* and *ākhar*.

V. THE ORIGIN OF THE *SHUHŪR SAN*

Although finding date equivalencies of *Shuhūr San* dates is of primary importance to most scholars, the introduction of the era is of historical interest. Several epigraphists have tentatively assigned the date of the era's introduction, but the evidence available does not justify their specificity. Since V. S. Bendrey's discussion includes material not found elsewhere, his comments are given in full:

It is believed that the Arabic era originated from the ascension of *Mustak* to the throne of his father *Abraha* in 589 A.D. The first year of the era, however, coincided with 600 A.D., and its commencement occurred in the latter half of May 600 A.D. Another version of the origin of this era is that the era may have been an off-shoot of the *Hijrā* reckoning probably originated in or closely about the year 745 A.H. (i.e. May 15th, 1344 to 3rd May 1345 A.D.), and it may have been introduced in the southern part of *Mahārāṣṭra* by *Muḥammad Tughluq* during his regime. This view finds support in the circumstance that a new era was introduced by the *Jawhar* Chief in commemoration of his investiture with "Shah"-ship by *Muḥammad Tughluq*. Whatever be the origin of the era, it is definitely ascertained from the records now available that its initial point must be taken as 600 A.D. for our calculation of this era.¹

The reasons for Bendrey's conclusions concerning the Arabic *San* are not clear. Firstly, *Abraha* and his son were Ethiopian rulers of Yemen during the period of Ethiopian ascendancy (A.D. 529 to 606) in that area. If the title originated with either of them, since they were not Arabs, they must have been identifying an already extant era; but Bendrey gives no evidence that such an era was in effect in Yemen. And had either of these rulers originated the era himself, one would expect to find the title reflecting their Ethiopian heritage or carrying some reference to their own names. Secondly, there is no indication of which records "now available" demonstrate "that its initial date must be taken as 600 A.D.". Has Bendrey simply subtracted the 599/600 discrepancy between the Christian era to arrive at this figure; and if so, then the correct answer would be from the latter half of May 599, not 600. Also, if the era was instituted in 589, why were the years not numbered until 600? And finally, since the calculation of the beginning of each *Shuhūr* year is based on a Hindu solar calculation, and since the period of the year is so well suited to Deccani conditions, it suggests most strongly that the era was not imported but was native to the area.

¹ Bendrey, *Study of Muslim Inscriptions (Bombay, 1944)*, p. 33.

This last statement is highly suggestive, in that it implies that the official introduction of the era for record-keeping purposes was simply a recognition of the suitability of an extant way of dividing the year. It is common knowledge that amongst different communities in the sub-continent the actual beginning of the year for calendar purposes does not necessarily correspond with the beginning of the year for other purposes. For example, the Mārwarī book-keeping year begins officially with Lakṣmī Pujā, not with either the calendar year or the tax year. In the Deccan, the "Mirg" was the beginning of the cultivators' year, and at some point some one in officialdom seems to have recognised the suitability of this year for land and land revenue records. So that actually what is being discussed in terms of fixing the "origin" of this era is, when did the suitability of the agricultural year for record-keeping purposes become apparent, and when was the agricultural year first used as an official record-keeping year?

Returning to Bendrey's analysis, it is suggested as it was in Grant Duff that the origins of the Shuhūr San lie in the period of Muḥammad Tughluq's domination of the Deccan. Other ephe-merists comment on this point, but their explanations lack detail. C. S. Patell, for example, says :

According to Jervis, it was introduced on the 6th of June, 1342 A.D., in 743 of the Hegira ; others place it a year sooner. He states that the computation of its agreement with the Hegira year shows it to have begun when the 745th Hegira (A.C. 1344) corresponded with the 745th Shuhur San.¹

And R. Sewell and S. B. Dikshit say :

It only diverged from the Hijra in A.D. 1344, according to the best computation, since when it has been a solar year as described above. On May 15th A.D. 1344, the Hijra year 745 began. But since then the Shahur reckoning was carried on by itself as a solar year.²

The basic assumption underlying the two statements above, Bendrey's comments, and Grant Duff's description, is that when the Shuhūr era was introduced, it bore the same number as the Hijri year current, just as the various Faṣlī eras did ; but, given the solar nature of the era, each year was longer than each Hijri year, so that through time the numbering of the years diverged, the Hijri system moving ahead by about three years per century.

A common factor in all four descriptions is the reference to the year A.H. 745, but the commentaries are speculative and contradictory. The Patell statement is internally inconsistent—the era was introduced on 6 June 1342 (which was 1 Muḥarram 743) or a year earlier, but it began in 745. Bendrey hedges by saying that it originated "in or closely around" 745. Grant Duff says, "By calculation, it appears" to have been introduced in 745. And Sewell and Dikshit say that it "diverged" from the Hijri year in 745. These contradictions are the result of various fallacious assumptions. Jervis, for example, was aware that in the nineteenth century the "Mirg" fell in early June, so he apparently searched for an early June date when 1 Muḥarram might have corresponded with the "Mirg"—as in 1277, 1342, and 1375. The year 1342 seemed most suitable given the 599 year discrepancy between the Shuhūr and Christian eras. Unfortunately, he neglected to take into account the calendar reform of 1752 before which the "Mirg" would have taken place in May, not in June. The Sewell and Dikshit statement suggests that, since A.H. 745 began on 15 May and the Shuhūr year began later, the dates diverged at that time. This assumes, incorrectly, one of two things : either (1) that the Shuhūr year and the Hijri year were identified by the same number before 745; or (2) that since the Hijri year began before the Shuhūr

¹ Cowasjee Sorābjee Patell, *Cowasjee Patell's Chronology* (London, 1866), p. 55.

² Robert Sewell and Sankara Bālkrishna Dikshit, *The Indian Calendar* (London, 1896), p. 45.

year, the Shuhūr year would have had a different number—but this is when the Shuhūr year would have had the same number.

In order to resolve the problems above, Table 1 has been constructed showing when it was possible for the Shuhūr and the Hijrī year to be identified with the same number. Column 1 gives the number of the Hijrī year; column 2, the equivalent Christian date of the first day of that Hijrī year, of 1 Muharram; column 3, the last day of that Hijrī year; column 4, the first day of the Shuhūr year; column 5, the Shuhūr year; and column 6 the Hijrī year current when the Shuhūr year began. The asterisks identify years when the Hijrī year and Shuhūr year were not the same.

A.H. 741 began on 27 June 1340. The Shuhūr year and the first day of that year can be calculated with the method explained previously in this essay. 1340 minus 599 gives the Shuhūr year 741. In 1340, the first day of Mēsha-Chittirai was 26 March. 26 plus 56 equals 82, and 82 minus 62 equals 20. 1 May plus 20 equals 21 May. So the first day of Shuhūr 741 was 21 May 1340. The Hijrī year 741, however, did not begin until the end of June—in other words, the Hijrī year current when 1 Shuhūr San 741 would have taken place was 740. Therefore, if the assumption that when the Shuhūr year was introduced it was identified with the number of the Hijrī year current is correct, it could not have been introduced in A.H. 741 (1340 A.D.). Following this procedure, all the Hijrī dates from 741 through 781 have been given along with the Shuhūr dates.

Examining the table, one can see that it was possible for the Hijrī and Shuhūr years to be identified with the same number only from A.H. 745 through 776 (A.D. 21 May 1344 through 1 June 1375). The Shuhūr year, therefore, could not have been introduced before A.H. 745, nor after A.H. 776. And the two eras “diverged” in A.H. 777 (1375 A.D.), not in the period of the 740's.

The numerical evidence alone does not establish the exact year in which the era was first used for book-keeping purposes. It does make highly dubious the assertion that it was introduced by Muhammad Tughluq since from 21 May 1344—the earliest date the era could have been introduced as seen above—he was absent from the Deccan and returned only in 1345 for the siege of Daulatābād. Conditions in the Deccan were extremely unsettled in 1344-45, and political hegemony was not restored until after the establishment of the Bahmanī dynasty in 1347. It seems far more likely that the era was first used officially by the Bahmanīs between 1347 and 1375 while creating and consolidating their own political and revenue structures, rather than during the confusion of the political collapse of the Tughluqs.

There now remains Bendrey's statement about the “Jawhar Chief”. This may be a reference to an officer named Malik Jauhar,¹ but the Persian source—which Bendrey does not give—must be studied closely. The statement as given is clearly ambiguous—most political leaders take great pride in introducing a “new era”. Usually this is a figurative statement; and when it is literal, it means enumerating years from the time of the ruler's accession rather than introducing a new system.

VI. HINDU LUNI-SOLAR TERMS RELEVANT TO UNDERSTANDING SHUHÜR SAN CALCULATIONS

The section describing the method for calculating Shuhūr San date equivalencies was presented without explanation because of the complexities of Hindu calendar calculations. In

¹ By “Jawhar Chief” is intended the Chief or Rāja of the erstwhile Jawhār State situated within the geographical limits of Thāna District, near Bombay. Prof. Bendrey has perhaps derived his information from the *Imperial Gazetteer of India*, Vol. XIV (London, 1908), p. 88, which too, unfortunately, does not quote any source. Thus any reference to an officer Malik Jauhar is out of question; Miss Martin was misled by the similarity of names. Nevertheless, there is no doubt that this particular piece of information needs further scrutiny and study as stated by Miss Martin.—Ed.

order to understand why the method presented is accurate and also to indicate under what circumstances there may be discrepancies in Pillai's tables affecting the *Shuhūr San*, it is necessary to examine certain aspects of the Hindu luni-solar calendar, and also to consider certain assumptions made by Pillai when compiling his tables.

i. THE LUNI-SOLARY YEAR, SIDDHĀNTAS AND ANKRĀNTIS

Indian calendar systems generally follow the same procedural rules for calculations; however, the constants used to define the length of certain astronomical periods may differ slightly. These constants define systems which are called *siddhāntas*; and there are two major *siddhāntas* in use in the sub-continent. One of these systems, the *Surya Siddhānta*, is found throughout the sub-continent; the other, the *Ārya Siddhānta*, is used in the South. The only difference between the two systems occurs in the fixing of the time of the exact moment of *Sankrānti*—the beginning of each solar month; and, for the centuries with which this essay is concerned, this involves a difference of .06 to .11 of a day.

The luni-solar year used in India is calculated on the basis of both lunar and solar phenomena. The solar calculations involve the sidereal year—a year measured in terms of the time required for the earth to move around the sun and return to a particular position determined in relation to the (apparently) fixed stars. Each of the twelve months of the solar year begins when the sun enters a different *rāśi*—Sign of the Zodiac—and the exact moment of its entrance is called a *sankrānti*. Pillai suggests that it is helpful to think of these solar months as “hinges” and to consider the lunar months as “doors” which swing on the hinges.¹

The moment of *Mēsha Sankrānti*—the phenomenon which determines the beginning of the solar year and the first day of the first solar month—is a “hinge”, and the new moon which precedes this *sankrānti* starts the lunar month associated with that *sankrānti*—it is the door hanging on the *Mēsha Sankrānti* hinge. On the second *sankrānti* of the year, the next lunar month is hung, beginning on the new moon which precedes that *sankrānti*. Usually (but not always) the solar months have a regular number of days, varying from 29 to 31, depending on the month. The actual length of the lunar month, however, is 29.53 days. It is possible, then, for a month of 30 or 31 days to have two new moons; and that solar month will then have two lunar months commencing within it. Much more rarely, there is no new moon in a 29 day solar month, and so a lunar month is dropped from the calendar in that year.

As stated above, the length of the regular solar months ranges from 29 to 31 days. Occasionally, however, the regular month may contain an extra day. This happens in the *Tamilnāḍu* system when the moment of *Sankrānti* occurs after sunset.² Instead of beginning the new month immediately, it is not extended by one day. It is for this reason that a particular date in a single solar month cannot be identified as always occurring 56 days after *Mēsha Sankrānti*. And, therefore, in every year the calculation of the day the sun enters the *Nakshatra Mrigāsīras* must be calculated by the addition of the 56 day difference.

ii. THE LUNI-SOLAR DAY, NAKSHATRAS AND TITHIS

There are two ways of defining daily time in the Hindu luni-solar system. One of these is in terms of *nakshatras*. In non-technical terms, a *nakshatra* corresponds to a lunar mansion, and

¹ Pillai, *op. cit.*, p. 25.

² For a more detailed explanation, see sub-section iii. The Indian Civil Day.

there are 27 lunar mansions in the Hindu calendar system. From the point of view of an observer on the earth, this nakshatra cycle is complete when the moon has travelled around the earth until it has regained its position in regard to a fixed group of stars identified as a particular nakshatra—a period of a little over 27·32 days. Since there are 27 nakshatras, the time unit of one nakshatra is equal to a little more than one day, say about 1 day 18 minutes.

The other method of defining daily time is based upon the time required for the moon to move from one new moon to the next. This period is about 29·53 days long, during which the moon not only travels around the earth but also travels with the earth in its orbit. In so doing, it moves to a point further in the earth's orbit, and in order for the sun's rays to be blocked out sufficiently for another new moon to occur, it must move further around the earth as well. There are 30 tithis in this lunar period, so that one tithi is slightly less than the western day, say about ·98 of a day.

As daily time-keeping units, nakshatras and tithis have no effect on the *Shuhūr San*. The term nakshatra, however, is used in regard to fixing the first day of the *Shuhūr* year which occurs when the sun enters the Nakshatra *Mrigasiṛas*. A more technical definition of a nakshatra is the portion of the ecliptic occupied by the moon on successive days. Since the ecliptic is the apparent path of the sun through the stars over a period of a year, the sun also moves through the 27 nakshatras. And just as the sun moves around and appears to re-enter the constellation *Mēsha* once a year, it also will pass through each nakshatra at a particular time each year. In his footnote referred to above, Pillai calculates this time by measuring the distance between the point of *Mēsha Sankrānti* and the point which indicates the entrance of the sun into *Mrigasiṛas* in degrees of longitude and then converts this measurement into days. Since the stars involved are so distant as to seem to be fixed, this distance is a constant, and the time required to traverse it is also a constant. Thus the sun's entrance into the Nakshatra *Mrigasiṛas* always occurs 56 days after *Mēsha Sankrānti*.

iii. THE INDIAN CIVIL DAY

On a day-to-day basis, time is kept according to the divisions of the Indian Civil Day. This day begins at sunrise, not at midnight, and is split into 60 units called *ghaṭikās*. Pillai has used the civil day as the basis for his calculations, and when he cites the moment of *Mēsha Sankrānti* at the top of the page of his Ephemeris dealing with each year, he has expressed that moment in decimal places of the civil day. For example, in 1400 A.D., *Mēsha Sankrānti* took place on 26·24 March according to the *Surya Siddhānta*. Checking either the book-marker or end-sheet, the decimal ·24 of a day equals 14 and $\frac{1}{2}$ *ghaṭikās*, or 5 hours 45 minutes. This time is reckoned from sunrise; if sunrise were at 6:00 A.M., then the time indicated would be 5 hours 45 minutes later, or 15 minutes before noon. Assuming that the mean sunrise time for India is 6:00 A.M., then any fraction over ·75 of a day, or over 45 *ghaṭikās*, would take place after midnight; and in western terms that would put it into the following day.

In different parts of India there are different calculations for the commencement of the civil day. In Orissā, irrespective of the moment of *Sankrānti*, the first day of the solar month begins on the actual day (i.e. civil day, calculated from sunrise to sunrise) of the *sankrānti*. In areas of Malabār, if *sankrānti* occurs before 18 *ghaṭikās* have expired, then that civil day is the civil *sankrānti* day; if *sankrānti* occurs after 18 *ghaṭikās* have expired, then the next civil day is identified as the *sankrānti* day. In Tamilnāḍu, the cut-off point is 30 *ghaṭikās*; if *sankrānti* occurs when 30 *ghaṭikās* have expired, then the next civil day is identified as the *sankrānti* day. And in Bengāl, when *sankrānti* occurs during the first 45 *ghaṭikās* of a day, the next

day is the civil sankrānti day; if it takes place after 45 ghaṭikās, the following day is the civil day.¹

Examining Pillai's tables once again, two things should be noted about the relationship between the moment of Mēsha Sankrānti and the first day of the first solar month, 1 Mēsha-Chittirai. Pillai gives two calculations for the moment of Mēsha Sankrānti, one in the Surya Siddhānta, one in the Ārya Siddhānta. In his tables he gives date equivalencies of Mēsha-Chittirai and the Christian date. Whenever the moment of Mēsha Sankrānti according to the Ārya Siddhānta corresponds to .50 of a day or more, 1 Mēsha Chittirai corresponds to the next Christian day. For example, in 1436, Mēsha-Chittirai took place at 26.56 March according to the Ārya Siddhānta. Pillai gives the day of 1 Mēsha-Chittirai as 26 March. In 1440 however, Mēsha Sankrānti took place at 26.69 March in the Surya Siddhānta and at 26.52 according to the Ārya Siddhānta. In this case Pillai gives the date equivalency of 1 Mēsha-Chittirai as 27 March. Pillai has used the Tamilnāḍu system for calculating the civil day in his tables, as well as the Ārya Siddhānta, and both of these are southern systems. Nowhere is it made explicit, however, that the various rulers of the Deccan from the fourteenth through the nineteenth centuries used these two southern systems exclusively for their astronomical calculations.

The effect on the calculation of Shuhūr San dates, if other systems were used, would only occur when certain time periods were involved. Had the Surya Siddhānta been used rather than the Ārya Siddhānta, since the difference is .06 of a day in the fourteenth century and .11 of a day by the end of the nineteenth century, very few dates would have been affected, and only those dates where Mēsha Sankrānti took place at a crucial moment of the civil day. If one of the other three systems of computing the civil day had been used, then only during certain portions of a day would there have been an effect on establishing 1 Mēsha-Chittirai from the moment of Mēsha Sankrānti. In the Malabār system, times from .30 to .50 of a day would not convert to the next day as the Tamilnāḍu system does; and in the Bengāl system, times from .50 to .75 of a day would be the same as the Tamil system; all other times would be one day advanced.

The circumstances under which a discrepancy might be discovered are limited. When there is an accompanying Hijrī date, since the method presented uses Hijrī tables for finding the equivalent Christian date, there will be no discrepancy. In cases when only a Shuhūr date is available for establishing the first or last day of the Shuhūr year, there is a possibility of error. The only way this error can be detected and rectified is if a document clearly states that particular serial day of the Shuhūr year fell on a Hijrī date (or Hindu date, for that matter) of such-and-such, and it can then be demonstrated that the moment of Mēsha Sankrānti which began that Shuhūr year fell into one of the vital time periods listed in the preceding paragraph.

Recalling what was said earlier in the essay about the introduction of the Shuhūr San suggests that it is more probable that these two southern systems have been used rather than the other systems. To begin with, the Shuhūr San was first introduced in the South, not in the North. It was not until some two centuries later that it appeared in the North as the Faṣlī era. Furthermore, it seems to have been introduced by the Bahmanīs, a southern dynasty despite their northern origins, the strength of whose kingdom was dependent upon the agricultural conditions of the South. As the Shuhūr San was applied to Deccani conditions and used Hindu dating calculations for setting its initial day, it is logical to anticipate that local personnel would be used to establish important moments in that local system. Since the Tamilnāḍu system of calculations was the most widespread in the Bahmanī areas—the Bengāl system being far removed, and the Orissā

¹ See Pillai, *op. cit.*, p. 3.

and Malabār systems being confined to relatively small regions removed from the areas of Bahranī dominance—it is the most likely system to have been employed.

VII. 1 MĒSHA-CHITTIRAI EQUIVALENCIES : AN UNUSUAL PATTERN

An examination of Pillai's calculations for the date of 1 Mēsha-Chittirai indicates an unusual pattern of date-changes which repeats itself over a period of a little more than a century (see Table 2, *infra*). The reason for this strange looking pattern has to do with the discrepancy in the Christian calendar calculations between the real length of the year and the length used for calendar calculations. The real length of the year is 365 days 3 hours 48 minutes and 45 seconds, or slightly less than 365 and 1/4 days. Every four years an extra day is added to correct the calendar, but since the real calculation is a little less than 1/4 of a day per year, this extra day slightly overcompensates for the real discrepancy. In order to demonstrate exactly what happens, Table 3 has been prepared. For convenience in reckoning, the length of the year has been rounded off to 365 days 5 hours and 48 minutes. In terms of a fraction of a day, 5 hours and 48 minutes equal 348 minutes over 1440 minutes or 87/360ths. The years are imaginary, beginning with XX01, and each year evenly divisible by 4 (e.g., XX04, XX08, XX48) is a leap year.

Following the table, the year XX01 expires after 365 days, but there are 87/360ths of a day left in the real year, so the calendar is missing that fraction of a day, it is minus 87/360ths of a day. The year XX02 will also be a 365 day year, losing another 87/360ths, so that the total time discrepancy will be minus 174/360ths. The same situation applies to the third year, the total time lag at the end of XX03 being minus 261/360ths. The year XX04, being divisible by 4, will be a leap year of 366 days and plus 360/360ths of a day are added; however, the real addition of time is (minus 87/360) times (4), or minus 348/360ths. The calendar has added plus 360/360ths, so that the calendar has moved ahead of the real time by plus 12/360ths. In next year, XX05, 87/360ths are lost again, and the calendar is once more behind real time, the sum of a positive 12/360ths and a negative 87/360ths being minus 75/360ths. Expanding the table to cover 120 years (because a fairly small and regular fraction has been used), the table comes around to the beginning again as far as the fractions are concerned, and one whole day has been added.

Analysing the contents of the table, it begins with a pattern of three minus signs and one plus sign: then it moves to a pattern of two minus signs and two pluses; the next shift is to a pattern of one minus and three pluses; the fourth change is to a pattern of four pluses; finally the pattern is one day extra along with the original pattern of three minus signs and one plus sign.

Comparing this pattern with the dates of 1 Mēsha-Chittirai from 1348 to 1479, the same pattern is seen (the years do not correspond exactly because the fraction used to compute Table 3 was rounded off rather than a precise fraction). Beginning in 1348, there are three minus years in a row—that is 26 March—and in 1351 a plus year, or 27 March. This pattern repeats for some years. Then in 1379 the pattern changes to two minus and two plus days—i.e., 26, 26, 27, 27 March. In 1406 there is a shift to one minus and three plus days—i.e., 26, 27, 27, 27 March. In 1437 the pattern of all pluses emerges—i.e., 27, 27, 27, 27, March. And in 1467 an entire new day is added, the 28th of March, and the original pattern of three minus and one plus day begins again—i.e., 27, 27, 27, 28 March.

VIII. ANOTHER TABLE FOR CONVERSION

Many scholars working with South Asian materials may not have continuous access to Pillai's *An Indian Ephemeris*, and moreover, it is difficult to carry when on tour. A small, fairly inex-

pensive volume which is available (originally priced at Sh. 10/50, now perhaps slightly more) is G. S. P. Freeman-Grenville's *The Muslim and Christian Calendars*, London, Oxford University Press, 1963. One drawback to the volume is that the user has to calculate date equivalencies; however, the method is quite simple and can be learned very easily by anyone who is not petrified when faced with normal addition and subtraction. Furthermore, dates in this volume covering the centuries when the *Shuhūr San* was in use agree with the dates in the *Ephemeris* with two exceptions: the Freeman-Grenville volume follows the Gregorian reform of 1582, and there is an error in assigning the week day corresponding with 1 January from 1582 through 1878.

For adapting dates up to the calendar reform of 1582 and after the calendar reform of 1752, the following method can be used:—

(1) On a separate sheet of paper, convert the 1 Mēsha-Chittirai dates of 25, 26, 27 March, etc., and 9, 10, 11 April, etc., to their appropriate dates corresponding with the sun's entry into the Nakshatra Mṛigasīras 56 days later.

(2) Using Pillai's tables for 1 Mēsha-Chittirai, along with the list of equivalencies prepared in 1 above, 25 March will be immediately understood as 20 May, 26 March as 21 May, etc.

(3) In the Freeman-Grenville volume in the column labelled "Christian date to Muḥarram 1", on the right side, enter the correct date of the entrance of the sun into the Nakshatra Mṛigasīras corresponding with each Christian year. The column will then read 15 May 1344-21/5; 4 May 1345-21/5; 21 April 1346-21/5; etc. It is easiest to make the entry after the Christian year (rather than before the Hijri year) because every 33 years or so two Hijri years will begin in the same Christian year (1356, 1388, 1421, etc.).

(4) Then treat the date which has been entered with the same method with which all dates in the Freeman-Grenville volume are treated.

Dates in the *Ephemeris* were not reformed until 1752, while the Freeman-Grenville dates are reformed from 1582. So that the tables may be internally consistent, it is necessary to correct the Pillai figures when entering them into the Freeman-Grenville tables. Since 4 October became 14 October in 1582, Pillai dates such as 28 and 29 May will be converted to 7 and 8 June. In 1700 with the leap year day, the discrepancy becomes one day more. By keeping the table in the Freeman-Grenville volume consistent, all dates in the volume can be used the same way. And any figure which is the result of a series of calculations can then be converted at the end to correspond with the English calendar.

The error in assigning the week day corresponding with 1 January is a systematic error from the year 1552 through 1878. Each 365 day Christian year consists of 52 weeks and 1 day, so that if a year begins on a Sunday it also ends on a Sunday, and the next year begins on Monday. In leap years, because of the addition of an extra day, if a year begins on Sunday, then the following year begins on Tuesday. In 1551 the year began on Thursday; in 1552, then, it began on Friday. Freeman-Grenville has put back the day to Wednesday instead of advancing it to Friday, so that from 1552 onward, until 1871, all days are two days out of phase. During this period, whenever Thursday is given as the first day of the year, it must be corrected to read Saturday; when Monday is given, it must be corrected to read Wednesday, etc. In addition there is a typographical error in the year 1705; Saturday is given, but Sunday would be correct in terms of the systematic error. From 1872 through 5 January 1878 the error is reduced to only one day, and those eight years must be corrected by the addition of one day—Wednesday should be corrected to read Thursday, etc.

TABLE 1

YEARS WHEN THE HIJRI AND SHUHÜR YEARS COULD HAVE BORNE THE SAME NUMBER

Hijri Year	First Day of Hijri Year	Last Day of Hijri Year	First Day of <u>Shuhūr</u> Year	<u>Shuhūr</u> Year	Hijri Year Current on First Day of <u>Shuhūr</u> Year	Asterisks indicate years when Hijri & <u>Shuhūr</u> Numbers Differed
741	27/6/1340	16/6/1341	21/5/1340	741	740	*
742	17/6/1341	5/6/1342	21/5/1341	742	741	*
743	6/6/1342	25/5/1343	21/5/1342	743	742	*
744	26/5/1343	14/5/1344	21/5/1343	744	743	*
745	15/5/1344	3/5/1345	21/5/1344	745	745	
746	4/5/1345	23/4/1346	21/5/1345	746	746	
747	24/4/1346	12/4/1347	21/5/1346	747	747	
748	13/4/1347	31/3/1348	21/5/1347	748	748	
749	1/4/1348	21/3/1349	21/5/1348	749	749	
750	22/3/1349	10/3/1350	21/5/1349	750	750	
751	11/3/1350	27/2/1351	21/5/1350	751	751	
752	28/2/1351	17/2/1352	22/5/1351	752	752	
753	18/2/1352	5/2/1353	21/5/1352	753	753	
754	6/2/1353	23/1/1354	21/5/1353	754	754	
755	24/1/1354	15/1/1355	21/5/1354	755	755	
756	16/1/1355	4/1/1356	22/5/1355	756	756	
757	25/1/1356	24/12/1356	21/5/1356	757	757	
758	25/12/1356	14/12/1357	21/5/1357	758	758	
759	15/12/1357	2/12/1358	21/5/1358	759	759	
760	3/12/1358	22/11/1359	22/5/1359	760	760	
761	23/11/1359	10/11/1360	21/5/1360	761	761	
762	11/11/1360	30/10/1361	21/5/1361	762	762	

Hijri Year	First Day of Hijri Year	Last Day of Hijri Year	First Day of <u>Shuhūr</u> Year	<u>Shuhūr</u> Year	Hijri Year Current on First Day of <u>Shuhūr</u> Year	Asterisks indicate years when Hijri & <u>Shuhūr</u> Numbers Differed
763	31/10/1361	20/10/1362	21/5/1362	763	763	
764	21/10/1362	9/10/1363	22/5/1363	764	764	
765	10/10/1363	27/9/1364	21/5/1364	765	765	
766	28/9/1364	17/9/1365	21/5/1365	766	766	
767	18/9/1365	6/9/1366	21/5/1366	767	767	
768	7/9/1366	27/8/1367	22/5/1367	768	768	
769	28/8/1367	15/8/1368	21/5/1368	769	769	
770	16/8/1368	4/8/1369	21/5/1369	770	770	
771	5/8/1369	25/7/1370	21/5/1370	771	771	
772	26/7/1370	14/7/1371	22/5/1371	772	772	
773	15/7/1371	2/7/1372	21/5/1372	773	773	
774	3/7/1372	22/6/1373	21/5/1373	774	774	
775	23/6/1373	11/6/1374	21/5/1374	775	775	
776	12/6/1374	1/6/1375	22/5/1375	776	776	
777	2/6/1375	20/5/1376	21/5/1376	777	778	*
778	21/5/1376	9/5/1377	21/5/1377	778	779	*
779	10/5/1377	29/4/1378	21/5/1378	779	780	*
780	30/4/1378	18/4/1379	22/5/1379	780	781	*

TABLE 2

THE PATTERN OF 1 MĒSHA-CHITTIRAI EQUIVALENCIES, 1348-1479

Year	March Date of 1 Mēsha-Chittirai	One Plus Sign Indicates One Day's Advance From 26 March
1348	26	
1349	26	
1350	26	
1351	27	+
1352	26	
1353	26	
1354	26	
1355	27	+
1356	26	
1357	26	
1358	26	
1359	27	+
1360	26	
1361	26	
1362	26	
1363	27	+
1364	26	
1365	26	
1366	26	
1367	27	
1368	26	
1369	26	
1370	26	
1371	27	
1372	26	

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Year	March Date of 1 Mēsha-Chittirai	One Plus Sign Indicates One Day's Advance From 26 March
1373	26	
1374	26	
1375	27	+
1376	26	
1377	26	
1378	26	
1379	27	+
1380	26	
1381	26	
1382	27	+
1383	27	+
1384	26	
1385	26	
1386	27	+
1387	27	+
1388	26	
1389	26	
1390	27	+
1391	27	+
1392	26	
1393	26	
1394	27	+
1395	27	±
1396	26	
1397	26	
1398	27	+
1399	27	+

Year	March Date of 1 Mēsha-Chittirai	One Plus Sign Indicates One Day's Advance From 26 March
1400	26	
1401	26	
1402	27	+
1403	27	+
1404	26	
1405	26	
1406	27	+
1407	27	+
1408	26	
1409	27	+
1410	27	+
1411	27	+
1412	26	
1413	27	+
1414	27	+
1415	27	+
1416	26	
1417	27	+
1418	27	+
1419	27	+
1420	26	
1421	27	+
1422	27	+
1423	27	+
1424	26	
1425	27	+
1426	27	+

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Year	March Date of 1 Mēsha-Chittirai	One Plus Sign Indicates One Day's Advance From 26 March
1427	27	+
1428	26	
1429	27	+
1430	27	+
1431	27	+
1432	26	
1433	27	+
1434	27	+
1435	27	+
1436	26	
1437	27	+
1438	27	+
1439	27	+
1440	27	+
1441	27	+
1442	27	+
1443	27	+
1444	27	+
1445	27	+
1446	27	+
1447	27	+
1448	27	+
1449	27	+
1450	27	+
1451	27	+
1452	27	+
1453	27	+

Year	March Date of 1 Mēsha-Chittirai	One Plus Sign Indicates One Day's Advance From 26 March
1454	27	+
1455	27	+
1456	27	+
1457	27	+
1458	27	+
1459	27	+
1460	27	+
1461	27	+
1462	27	+
1463	27	+
1464	27	+
1465	27	+
1466	27	+
1467	27	+
1468	27	+
1469	27	+
1470	27	+
1471	28	++
1472	27	+
1473	27	+
1474	27	+
1475	28	++
1476	27	+
1477	27	+
1478	27	+
1479	28	++

TABLE 3

THE PATTERN OF CALENDAR YEAR AND REAL YEAR TIME DISCREPANCIES
(SEE SECTION VII. 1 MĒSHA-CHITTIRAI EQUIVALENCIES: AN UNUSUAL
PATTERN, FOR EXPLANATION)

Number of Year	Discrepancy
XX01	- 87/360
XX02	- 174/360
XX03	- 261/360
XX04	+ 12/360
XX05	- 75/360
XX06	- 162/360
XX07	- 249/360
XX08	+ 24/360
XX09	- 63/360
XX10	- 150/360
XX11	- 237/360
XX12	+ 36/360
XX13	- 51/360
XX14	- 138/360
XX15	- 225/360
XX16	+ 48/360
XX17	- 39/360
XX18	- 126/360
XX19	- 213/360
XX20	+ 60/360
XX21	- 27/360
XX22	- 114/360
XX23	- 201/360
XX24	+ 72/360

Number of Year	Discrepancy
XX25	— 15/360
XX26	— 102/360
XX27	— 189/360
XX28	+ 84/360
XX29	— 3/360
XX30	— 90/360
XX31	— 177/360
XX32	+ 96/360
XX33	+ 9/360
XX34	— 78/360
XX35	— 165/360
XX36	+ 108/360
XX37	+ 21/360
XX38	— 66/360
XX39	— 153/360
XX40	+ 120/360
XX41	+ 33/360
XX42	— 54/360
XX43	— 141/360
XX44	+ 132/360
XX45	+ 45/360
XX46	— 42/360
XX47	— 129/360
XX48	+ 144/360
XX49	+ 57/360
XX50	— 30/360
XX51	— 117/360

Number of Year	Discrepancy
XX52	+ 156/360
XX53	+ 69/360
XX54	- 18/360
XX55	- 105/360
XX56	+ 168/360
XX57	+ 81/360
XX58	- 6/360
XX59	- 93/360
XX60	+ 180/360
XX61	+ 93/360
XX62	+ 6/360
XX63	- 81/360
XX64	+ 192/360
XX65	+ 105/360
XX66	+ 18/360
XX67	- 69/360
XX68	+ 204/360
XX69	+ 117/360
XX70	+ 30/360
XX71	- 57/360
XX72	+ 216/360
XX73	+ 129/360
XX74	+ 42/360

Number of Year	Discrepancy
XX75	— 45/360
XX76	+ 228/360
XX77	+ 141/360
XX78	+ 54/360
XX79	— 33/360
XX80	+ 240/360
XX81	+ 153/360
XX82	+ 66/360
XX83	— 21/360
XX84	+ 252/360
XX85	— 165/360
XX86	+ 78/360
XX87	— 9/360
XX88	+ 264/360
XX89	+ 177/360
XX90	+ 90/360
XX91	+ 3/360
XX92	+ 276/360
XX93	+ 189/360
XX94	+ 102/360
XX95	+ 15/360
XX96	+ 288/360
XX97	+ 201/360

Number of Year	Discrepancy
XX98	+ 114/360
XX99	+ 27/360
X100	+ 300/360
X101	+ 213/360
X102	+ 126/360
X103	+ 39/360
X104	+ 312/360
X105	+ 225/360
X106	+ 138/360
X107	+ 51/360
X108	+ 324/360
X109	+ 237/360
X110	+ 150/360
X111	+ 63/360
X112	+ 336/360
X113	+ 249/360
X114	+ 162/360
X115	+ 75/360
X116	+ 348/360
X117	+ 241/360
X118	+ 174/360
X119	+ 87/360
X120	+1000/360

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